

A framework for modeling corrosion-related degradation in reinforced concrete

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ABSTRACT: The corrosion of the reinforcement steel is the most common cause of degradation of reinforced concrete. The repair work is always associated with high costs which is mainly due to lack of fundamental understanding of the processes of corrosion and cracking. In the literature, most degradation models are empirical and based on the assumptions, such as homogeneous concrete structure and uniform corrosion products growth from rebar. According to the steps of the corrosion-related degradation, this paper proposes a framework for modelling corrosion-related degradation in reinforced concrete. Models that can be related to each step in this framework are reviewed. The proposed framework can enhance the understanding of corrosion-related degradation for researchers and engineers.

1 GENERAL INSTRUCTIONS

Concrete is a porous solid that contains a highly alkaline liquid phase, so that pH is buffered well above 12.5 and the embedded reinforcement steel bar (rebar) is protected from corrosion by passivity. Corrosion can be triggered by the ingress of chloride – e.g. due to exposure to seawater or road deicing salts – and/or by carbonation of the concrete. Under these circumstances, corrosion products precipitate in the region around the interface between concrete and steel bar (known as steel-concrete interface, SCI (Angst et al. 2017)). With the growth of the corrosion products, pores at the SCI are gradually filled and stresses can be created during filling. When the generated stresses exceed a certain level (strength of concrete), cracking is apt to happen. Corrosion-induced cracking is a common limit state in service life considerations.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the service life (adapted from Tuutti (Tuutti 1982)).

As indicated in Fig. 1, three steps are generally involved in forecasting the corrosion-related degradation of reinforced concrete (RC) structures: i) modeling the transport of the corrosive agents through the concrete to the steel before the corrosion initiation; ii) describing corrosion initiation; and iii) modeling the corrosion propagation stage. The stage of mass transport and accumulation of the aggressive species at the steel is typically referred to as the initiation stage; initiation of corrosion marks the transition to the so-called propagation stage. The limit states for corroding RC structures are the loss of steel sectional area or corrosion-induced cracking of the concrete; both can affect the load bearing capacity and structural integrity, and thus the safety of a structure. Therefore, accurately predicting the time-to-cracking is essential to estimate the service life of RC structures.

A critical analysis concluded that the majority of models are only capable of adequately predicting the time-to-cracking for the experiments to which they were fitted (Jamali et al. 2013). The highly complex analytical and numerical models do not necessarily lead to more accurate predictions than those empirical models. One of main reasons is that these conventional approaches to simulate the corrosion-induced cracking considered corrosion products growth analogous to the expansion of rebar (e.g., hydraulic pressure-induced expansion from rebar in Allan (Allan 1995) and Uddin et al. (2004)), so there are two implications: corrosion products directly grow from rebar and the growth is uniform around rebar. Both of them are questionable. Aligizaki et al. (Aligizaki et al. 2000) observed that corrosion products could diffuse

away rebar and into the aggregate–paste interface in concrete. Recent SEM images showed that after being exposed to the sea water or NaCl solution for years corrosion products can penetrate into the concrete matrix and the distribution of them is not uniformly around rebar (Wong et al. 2010; Zhao et al. 2017).

The location of precipitation of corrosion products depends strongly on the local pore solution chemistry as well as ion movements. Concentration gradients in hydroxide and corrosive agents are very likely present from the steel surface into the bulk concrete as a result from the corrosion process and thus, precipitation may occur at different iron concentrations depending on the location. Quantifications of the portion of the released iron that precipitates directly at the steel surface and the portion that is able to move into the bulk concrete are lacking. Moreover, the interaction between the precipitation of corrosion products and the corrosion rate is related to the local pore structure. With the precipitation of solid corrosion products, the percentage of pore clogging is increasing and thus leads to the decrease of corrosion rate with time (Angst et al. 2011) Therefore, to accurately simulate corrosion-induced cracking, a model must take into account the whole process of corrosion, including the mesostructure of the SCI, moisture/ion transport, corrosion products formation and precipitation, and their influence on the mesostructure of the SCI.

Fig. 2. The proposed framework for modelling corrosion-induced cracking.

In this paper, a framework for modelling the corrosion-induced cracking in reinforced concrete is proposed (see Fig. 2). First, the structure of the SCI at the mesoscale must be well represented because the structure has a very close effect on the mass transport and the precipitation of corrosion products. The transport of moisture, ions and oxygen is then simulated in response to the external environment. The thermodynamic approach (chemical equilibrium) is used to predict the formation of corrosion products

and phase changes. When corrosion products grow at a certain location, the local structure is altered as more solids formed and can further affect mass transport. The growth of solid corrosion products induces stresses to the concrete matrix until the failure of concrete.

2 STRUCTURE OF SCI

The SEM images show that the thickness of the SCI, including millscale, water bleeding zone and corrosion product-filled paste, is generally in the scale of millimeter (Wong et al. 2010; Zhao et al. 2017). At this scale, the presence of aggregates can significantly affect the mass transport and the growth of corrosion products, and therefore the SCI could not be viewed as a homogeneous domain. Instead, the heterogeneous properties have to be considered in the numerical simulations.

The heterogeneity of a porous medium can be included through various ways, such as stochastic, dual-porosity and composite materials approaches. The stochastic approach views the transport property (e.g., permeability) as a random variable described by a specified space function. The randomness is highly dependent on the random space functions (RSFs) (Zhang, 2001). This approach has been widely used in studying water and contaminant transport in vadose zones (e.g., Russo et al. 1993; Tompson & Gelhar 1990). However, for transport phenomena in concrete, this approach is rarely used, because the scale is much smaller than groundwater transport and RSFs of transport properties for concrete are not feasible.

Taking the material as a dual-porosity porous medium is commonly found in the literature. The original proposal is to treat the porous medium as two domains, one associated with large pores or fractures where only advective flux occurs and the other one related to the low permeable pore system where advection is negligible (Gerke & van Genuchten 1993). Both of domains are treated as homogeneous media with different material and transport properties. The mass exchange between these two domains is formulated by a separate equation in response to the main variables (i.e., pressure for water and concentration for ions). In the dual-porosity approach, a medium is considered to be a superposition of these two domains, meaning that they are not physically separable. Therefore, a dual-porosity model is a conceptual model. For cementitious materials, two domains are not necessarily considered as two separated regions. It can be viewed as transport in large and small pores based on the assumption that transport mechanisms are different in pores with different sizes (Zhang et al. 2017).

The most common way to describe the structure of concrete is to treat it as a composite material, so that different material properties can be assigned for each

constituent. When modelling unsaturated moisture transport in heterogeneous limestone, Roels et al. (Roels et al. 2003) viewed the limestone consisting of two parts (walls and paste) with different moisture properties (e.g., permeability and sorption isotherm). For concrete, the commonly used structure construction method at the mesoscale is to separate it into coarse aggregates, interfacial transition zone (ITZ), and mortar matrix (cement paste with fine aggregates). The mortar matrix is a homogeneous medium with a certain size of fine aggregates being assumed to uniformly distribute in cement paste. In the study of Du et al. (Du et al. 2014), all the aggregates smaller than 2 mm are included in the mortar matrix. ITZ is considered as a uniform thin layer around each aggregate and the thickness is assigned as 500 μm which is much wider than the actual thickness of ITZ (e.g., 20 - 45 μm (Horne et al. 2007)). The purpose of using the relative large thickness is to ensure that ITZ can be reasonably meshed for simulations. The thickness of ITZ for various aggregates is the same because comparing with the size of aggregates ITZ is much smaller (Du et al., 2014). Abyaneh et al. (Abyaneh et al. 2013) set an exponential function for the porosity distribution in ITZ showing that ITZ porosity becomes the same as the bulk porosity at about 40 μm from the aggregate. The choice of method to heterogenize the material is always dependent on the size of the domain and the resolution of the simulations. The domain size in Du et al. (2014) is several centimeter, so a 500 μm thick ITZ can be meshed. Abyaneh et al. (Abyaneh et al. 2013) simulated water transport in a cube of 7.5 mm and a 40 μm ITZ can be captured. They found that to consider the effect of ITZ, the voxel size must be smaller than 16.7 μm which means that ITZ is divided into about two or three voxels. For even larger domain (e.g., above 10 cm), the zero-thickness interface element was employed for simulating thin ITZ structure (Li et al. 2017), meaning that no actual ITZ is meshed but when moisture moves around aggregates the transport coefficient (permeability) is much higher than that in bulk. However, these methods are too idealized because ITZ is not uniform around the aggregate. In contrast, it is always relying on the size of cement particles, the orientation of the aggregate and bleeding effects. In addition, the shapes of aggregates in concrete are not the ideal sphere, ellipsoid or oblate sphere.

Recently, Zhang et al. (Zhang et al. 2018) proposed a method called “image-based local homogenization method” to model mass transport at the SCI. Similar to the composite material approach, this method takes the SCI as the composite material. However, cement paste with fine aggregates is not considered as a homogeneous domain. Porosity at each point is directly calculated based on the gray level of the SEM-BSE image. An example of calculated porosity map in Fig. 3a shows that the water-

bleeding zone has extremely high porosity, while the aggregates have very low porosity.

Fig. 3. An example of calculating porosity based on the SEM-BSE image (a: porosity map; b: porosity profiles).

Porosity profiles along with the distance from aggregates were calculated based on the porosity map in Fig. 3a by using a similar algorithm to Horne et al. (Horne et al. 2007). Porosity profiles at different orientations for aggregates 1 and 2 in Fig. 3b show that the thickness of ITZ under aggregate 1 is about 40 μm and the upside of aggregate 2 seems very homogeneous with the thickness of ITZ about 5 μm . Measured thickness of ITZ for the other aggregates are in the range of 5 - 20 μm , which is in agreement with those values found in the literature (Scrivener et al. 2004; Horne et al. 2007). The narrow ITZ is caused by the wall effect (Scrivener et al. 2004) and the wide ITZ is closely related to the water bleeding effect. These results are able to demonstrate that the proposed method can reasonably describe the structure of the SCI.

3 MASS TRANSPORT MODEL

After Fe^{2+} is released from rebar, two processes will be mainly involved: transport and chemical reaction. Fe^{2+} can move in pore solution under the concentration gradient and with the convection of liquid water. Meanwhile, it can be oxidized to Fe^{3+} when oxygen is available and can further precipitate as corrosion products. Therefore, both mass transport and chemical reaction must be considered in the proposed framework. Moisture transport is important for the unsaturated concrete. When concrete is saturated,

moisture transport can be ignored for most cases. Regardless of the moisture condition, ion transport can be established under the concentration gradient or in an electric field. Chemical reactions for a complex system is commonly simulated by a thermodynamic approach. For cementitious materials, the local chemical equilibrium is generally assumed because the time scale for chemical reactions is much shorter than that for mass transport. However, the kinetic effect may be important for Fe^{2+} since corrosion products are found in concrete matrix which is believed that Fe^{2+} diffuses into concrete matrix and then is oxidized.

3.1 *Moisture transport*

Unsaturated moisture transport in concrete is related to many complex mechanisms which occur more or less jointly. In porous materials, several phenomena such as permeation, diffusion, adsorption-desorption-condensation and evaporation are very important. The diffusion processes are those of ordinary diffusion and Knudsen diffusion as put forward by Mason and Malinauskas (1983) and surface diffusion as reported by Higashi et al. (1963). The ordinary diffusion is caused by the gradient of concentration, so water molecules tend to diffuse from the high concentration region to the low concentration zone. Collisions between water molecules and exchange with adsorbed layer on pore walls can slow down the ordinary diffusion. This mechanism is dominant in pores with size between 50 nm and 10 μm (Xi et al. 1994) which is typically the size of capillary pores in cementitious materials. In addition to these large capillary pores, there are abundant small capillary and gel pores with size smaller than 50 nm where the Knudsen diffusion widely exists. When water molecules are mainly adsorbed by pore walls (which is the case if RH is low), they move near pore walls which is governed by leaps of water molecules between different adsorption sites. Generally, the ordinary diffusion is faster compared to other diffusion processes, so it represents the main part of mass diffusion. That is why, most studies focus on ordinary diffusion and neglect other types of diffusion.

If enough liquid in the pore network to create continuous liquid phase, capillary transport can be established under the gradient of capillary pressure in porous media. Owing to the strong capillarity, capillary transport can move much more mass than diffusion and can cause significant damage to the porous body. At the interface between liquid and vapor, evaporation-condensation occurs. This is not a transport mechanism but it can directly affect the transport of liquid and vapor. The transition between liquid and vapor is governed by the relative humidity imposed at the boundary of the simulation domain.

An ideal unsaturated moisture transport model is supposed to include all above-mentioned transport

mechanisms, while this kind of model is not sufficient. In the multiphase model introduced by Coussy (1995), the advection of liquid water (under the gradient of liquid pressure that is determined by capillary pressure) and the ordinary diffusion and advection (induced by gas pressure gradient) of water vapor and drying air were included. This model showed a good application for cementitious materials (Mainguy et al., 2001), in which the exchange between liquid and vapor was assumed to be dynamically (local) equilibrium and the sorption isotherm was described by Kelvin's law and van Genuchten equation (1980). If neglecting the effect gas pressure variations that are relatively small compared to liquid pressure (no pressure gradient for advection of vapor and dry air), the multiphase model can be reasonably simplified as a two-phase model with the advection of liquid and diffusion of water vapor. This version of moisture transport was widely used in the previous studies (Baroghel-Bouny 2007; Zhang et al. 2015; Zhang et al. 2016). Even simple models (diffusion-like equation) can be commonly found in the literature (e.g., Bazant and Najjar, 1972; Daian et al, 1988; Nilsson, 2002; Mainguy et al., 2001), while these models cannot simulate moisture transport at low RH which the diffusion of water vapor is dominant. Zhang and Scherer (2018) reported that without considering vapor diffusion a moisture transport model is less suitable for cementitious materials.

The case of non-equilibrium exchange between liquid and vapor was also investigated in the literature. Johannesson and his co-workers (Johannesson & Janz 2009; Jensen et al. 2014) introduced a linear function to represent the non-equilibrium mass exchange, while their results did not show that this consideration can improve the simulation accuracy. Hence, there may be no need to use a non-equilibrium model for cementitious materials.

Zhang et al. (Zhang et al. 2016) incorporated Knudsen diffusion into the two-phase moisture transport model with the help of additional measured pore size distribution. They found that Knudsen diffusion can significantly decrease the contribution of vapor diffusion to the total moisture transport, while it only has slight effect on liquid transport. In addition, compared with original two-phase model, the simulated mass change curves did not show any differences. Therefore, Knudsen diffusion may be not necessary for a moisture transport.

3.2 *Ion transport*

Mathematical models for ions transport started with the single-ion models, generally only considering ion diffusion (mainly chlorides for concrete) and its effect on durability of the cementitious materials. The advection can be included if liquid transport is present. These simplified models only work for the ideal solutions, in which interactions between these ions are

negligible. Nevertheless, ions are charged, so that they always interact with each other in a multispecies electrolyte like the pore solution in concrete. Therefore, an ion transport model must take into account the electric coupling of ions and their effect on ions transport. Otherwise, the simplification can certainly lead to high calculation errors for cementitious materials with highly concentrated pore solution.

In the past decades, it has been well recognized that the multispecies transport can be adequately modelled by the Poisson-Nernst-Planck (PNP) equations which includes the electrical coupling between the different ions (Samson & Marchand 1999). Under the concentration gradient, some ions diffuse faster than the others. If they have different charges, the electric fields could be created due to the speed difference. These fields can slow down diffusion of the fast ions and speed up the slow ions. This process can be modelled by PNP equations thanks to the Poisson equation, which is also used to fulfil the nil current assumptions.

In addition, ion transport is also a scale dependent process. On the pore walls, the electric double layer (EDL) which is formed as a result of the interaction of the ionized solution with static charges on the pore solid-liquid interface can facilitate (like charges) or slow down (opposite charges) ion movement. The thickness of the first layer (also known as Stern layer) is typically of one molecular diameter because of the molecular nature of the interface. Above this layer, the Debye's layer is formed, where the ion density varies smoothly. The thickness of the EDL can be determined by the Debye-Hückel approach as the distance from the solid charged interface for which the solid charge is screened by the counterions (Allaire et al. 2013). Outside Debye's layer, the solution can be considered as the bulk fluid without interactions with pore walls. The comparison with molecular dynamics simulations for clays (Marry et al. 2003) indicates that the Stern layer is globally negligible if the pore size is typically more than 1–2 nm. Presumably, this conclusion is also suitable for cementitious materials as no such study has been done. Thus, the Stern layer is less important for ion transport in concrete. The effects of the Debye's layer can be assumed as negligible for solutions with ionic strength lower than 300 mmol/l as reported by Samson and Marchand (Samson & Marchand 1999) who recorded a significant effect on the electrical potential but a negligible effect on concentration profiles.

4 THERMODYNAMICS MODELLING

The PNP equations only provide information about ion transport but cannot tell whether chemical reactions occur during the mass transport process. In many cases, only chloride is studied for the reactive transport because it is one of main causes to corrosion

of rebar. Various studies have shown that chlorides can be physically and chemically bound by C-S-H. To consider the phase change due to chlorides binding, empirical equations have been proposed. Baroghel-Bouny et al. (Baroghel-Bouny et al. 2012) compared various methods and found that all methods provided similar results which have a good agreement with the measurement. For the oxidation of Fe^{2+} , the reaction kinetic can provide reasonable results (Stefanoni et al. 2018). However, in most cases (e.g., corrosion), the complex chemical interactions and phase changes cannot be described by empirical equations. Therefore, the thermodynamic approach is needed to account chemical equilibrium calculations.

For cementitious materials, thermodynamic modelling has been used to calculate the composition of the pore solution and the hydrate assemblage during the hydration of cement (Lothenbach & Winnefeld 2006), to predict the phase change caused by carbonation (Shi et al. 2016) and to simulate chlorides ingress in mortar exposed to NaCl solution or sea water (Jensen et al. 2015). All these works were done by using geochemical solvers. According to Smith and Missen's classification (1982), chemical equilibrium algorithms are divided into two types: Gibbs energy minimization (GEM) method and law of mass-action (LMA) method. The former which needs the standard chemical potentials of the species includes geochemical packages such as Hch, FactSage and Gem-Selektor. The latter which requires the equilibrium constants of reactions includes WATEQ, CGESS and PHREEQC. The two types of thermochemical data are inter-convertible as has been well explained in the literature (e.g., Cheluget et al. 1987). It has been widely reported that both approaches are conceptually equivalent (Zeleznik and Gorden, 1968; Van Zeggeren and Storey, 1970). Therefore, the choice of the method to calculate chemical equilibrium will depend on the type of available thermodynamic data for the system.

Regarding cementitious materials, two commonly used solvers are Gem-Selektor (GEMS) (Lothenbach & Winnefeld 2006; Shi et al. 2016) and PHREEQC (Hosokawa et al., 2011; Jensen et al., 2015). A review of modern chemical reactive transport codes (Steeffel et al. 2015) shows that PHREEQC is capable of all selected geochemistry processes, including ion-association models that use Debye-Hückel formulations, the Pitzer specific-ion interaction model, and the specific-ion interaction theory (SIT) model. In addition to the wide range of geochemical capabilities offered by PHREEQC, its open-source continued support and development by the U.S. Geological Survey makes it as the most used geochemical solver.

A common problem for including chemical equilibrium modelling is that for each time step, equilibrium calculations must be performed for each cell, so that when thousands to millions of such calculations are needed, calculations speed can be much slowed

down. The use of parallelized calculations is one way to facilitate the calculations and both the latest versions of GEMS and PHREEQC (IPHREEQC) are completely parallelizable on HPC architectures. Another widely accepted way to promote the modelling of reactive transport is to use the "operator splitting" approach, which takes a bigger time step for chemical equilibrium calculations than the mass transport simulations. However, this comes at the cost of an error introduced by the splitting, so strategies have been devised to control this error. A recent study (Leal et al. 2017) employed a modified trust-region primal-dual interior-point algorithm to minimize Gibbs energy and claimed that the algorithm is very efficient, robust and accurate.

5 CORROSION PRODUCTS GROWTH AND CONCRETE CRACKING

As Fe^{2+} is released from rebar, a variety of corrosion products can be formed depending on the availability of oxygen. Precipitation of corrosion products in the concrete pores may give rise to expansive stresses and lead to concrete cracking and spalling. This process depends on factors, such as the presence of chloride and the structure of concrete matrix. The delayed cracking is often reported as the presence of chlorides which can strongly increase the solubility of corrosion products (Sagoe-Crentsil and Glasser, 1993) and therefore they can diffuse into the concrete matrix and away from rebar. It has been generally agreed that the concrete pore structure can accommodate a certain amount of corrosion products before expansive pressure, in particular, concrete is much porous or/and contains voids. Allan (1995) suggested that the time to cracking in concrete can be extended if the concrete is too porous. To account for the effect of corrosion products accommodated in pores, predictive models typically include a parameter termed as "porous zone" or "diffusion zone" (e.g., Liu and Weyers, 1998) which describes an idealized cylindrical void around the steel bar that first needs to be filled with corrosion products before expansive pressure arises. The expansive pressure that finally leads to concrete cracking is usually explained simply by the volume increase of (precipitated) corrosion products by a factor of ca. 2–7 with respect to the originally solid iron (e.g., Liu and Weyers, 1998). These simplifications are largely due to the fact that the mesostructure of the SCI and transport of corrosion products are not properly considered.

Indeed, it is well known that precipitates will only exert expansive stresses if they are forced to grow under confined conditions, such as against pore walls (Scherer, 1999; Flatt et al. 2014). Additionally, this growth must occur under supersaturated conditions, which dictate the crystallization pressure at the pore scale. Finally, the macroscopic stress will only arise

once a certain volume fraction of pores is filled by the crystallization compound. While these poromechanical considerations have in recent years been successfully applied in durability of concrete exposed to sulfate attack (Flatt & Scherer 2008), in conservation of stone (Flatt et al. 2014), and in geotechnics, its application to the specific case of corrosion products in concrete only received little attention (Scherer, 2012). Therefore, the use of poromechanical theory to predict corrosion products growth and the generated pressure is urgently needed.

6 SUMMARY

In this paper, a model framework that will be used to predict corrosion-induced cracking is proposed, which combines several models for different stages (see Fig. 2). The relevant models are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Relevant models for the proposed framework.

Stage	Option 1	Option 2
Structure	Homogeneous	Composite material
Moisture transport	Diffusion	Multiphase
Ion transport	Diffusion	PNP
Thermodynamic	GEMS	PHREEQC
Mechanics	Expansion	Poromechanics

Since a number of models have developed, for each stage more than one option can be chosen. Theoretically, any combinations of these models should be applicable for simulating the corrosion-induced cracking. However, through the review in this paper, it shows that simple assumptions are not appropriate to cementitious materials, such as homogeneous material structure, diffusion-like moisture and ion transport, and stresses generated by corrosion products growth analogous to hydraulic pressure expansion around rebar. For the chemical equilibrium modelling, PHREEQC is preferred because this geochemical solver has been widely used and numerous applications in the literature which can help us to couple it with mass transport and poromechanics models.

Acknowledgement

This study received funding from Swiss National Science Foundation (2-77104-16).

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